

A Study on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles Navigation Approaches Based on Artificial Intelligence

Dr. Ilam Parithi .T

Guest Lecturer in Computer Science, Government Arts and Science College

Sankarankovil, Tenkasi, Tamil Nadu

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524651>

Abstract

The (UAV) Unmanned Aerial Vehicles are a class of robotic aircraft that are capable of transportations of cargo and execution of aerial maneuvers under the guidance of remote control stations or as autonomous entities. This study aims to examine the different UAV navigation approaches (i.e) Optimization approach and Learning based approach and also discuss the various approaches of optimization approach and learning based approach such as Particle Swarm Optimization, Ant Colony Optimization, Deep Learning, Deep Reinforcement learning. These robotic devices comprise a wide range of vehicles, such as drones, micro and nano-aerial vehicles, which can travel across the air. The Lightweight micro-UAVs are now widely accessible using multispectral imaging sensors ranging from consumer-grade low-cost multispectral cameras to complicated high-end multisensory systems. UAVs, which initially were developed for military uses such as border patrol, are now widely utilized for a variety of functions including disaster observation and management, agricultural crop monitoring, chemical spraying in field crops, courier service, and firefighting.

Keywords: *UAV Classification, Optimization Approaches, Learning based Approaches*

1. Introduction

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) possess outstanding mobility, allowing them to operate effectively in distant regions lacking both physical and technical infrastructure. Initially, UAVs were only used for military purposes. Due to their growing influence, technical progress, and awareness among students in business and research, the uses of these technologies have expanded beyond military purposes. So many applications in which UAVs are now used include rescue operations, life-saving activities, agriculture and farming, pipeline inspections, transportation of commodities, pharmaceuticals, videotaping cinematography, and surveying. In addition to these, some further uses includes the management of inventories, the monitoring of surveillance activities, and offering services for relayed communications, when UAVs are actively utilized. Hence, they provide significant potential for use in a diverse range of sectors including both civilian and military spheres. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are implicated in addressing novel challenges and are engaged in a diverse range of innovative activities within the technical field, thereby contributing to the expansion of the UAV industry[1][3]. Furthermore, they are now being extensively investigated for their functionality as base stations in communication networks. Numerous organizations create Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in order to reduce service costs. Furthermore, several researches are now developing enhanced authentication techniques for UAV communications. Indeed, this will enhance the efficacy of UAV communications in the coming decades [4]. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have significant versatility, are readily deployable, and may be tailored to capture high-resolution photographs even during challenging operations. Furthermore, they have the capability to function in far places that are ordinarily physically unattainable, such as dense woodland regions and limited zones [2][5]. Only a small number of nations have implemented legislation to safeguard privacy of information pertaining to unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). New issues are presented as a result of the rise in the number of

unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), including the increase in air traffic, the laying of optimum pathways, the generation of flight plans, and the management of emergencies such as accidents, the management of UAV swarms, and cyber-physical assaults on UAVs [6]. When it comes to overcoming these obstacles, we are now using every single method that is available to us. Each new generation of technology, on the other hand, comes with its own set of constraints. Through the process of overcoming those limits, we were able to put technology in a position to replace the one that came before it.

2. UAV Classification

The intricate functions of (UAVs,) unmanned aerial vehicles, are due to the fact that they rely on mechanical as well as electrical power resources. Typically, these devices are equipped with an operating system on which the software for the UAV programs is executed [9][17]. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) may be categorized according to factors like flight mechanism, weight, flying height, and wing type. The table 1 describes the various characteristics of different UAVs. Moreover, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) may be classified based on their flying mechanism as follows

2.1 Multiple-rotor Wing UAV

The Vertical takeoff and landing are two of the capabilities that unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) possess. Additionally, UAVs are able to hover over a certain location. Nevertheless, their mobility is comparatively lower than that of other kinds of UAVs [7]. Furthermore, these UAVs require a greater amount of power since they must operate in the opposite direction of the gravitational pull. Multi-copters have the capability to vertically take off, land and levitate over a specific location. Therefore, their outstanding precision makes them very suitable for any usage [6][8]. Nevertheless, multi-copters have restricted duration of flight and use a substantial amount of energy due to their constant contra motion against gravity. A model of a UAV with multiple rotor wings is shown in figure 1 [a]. The benefits of this particular category of UAVs are its ease of deployment, affordability, lightweight design, and exceptional maneuverability. Simultaneously, these particular UAVs also include some constraints, such limited flight duration, accessibility within a very short range, heightened sensitivity to wind, and the ability to carry very small payloads.

Figure 1 Types of UAV based on wings
[a] Multirotator wing [b] Fixed Wing [c] Hybrid Wing

2.2. Fixed Wing UAVs

These unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are categorised as commercial aeroplanes, which means that in addition to being able to flow through the atmosphere and carry significant payloads, they are also able to glide through the air. Due to the fact that they use a different approach to flying than other kinds of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), they are able to achieve speeds that are far higher than

conventional UAVs. Having stated that, this specific attribute necessitates the use of a runway in order to carry out both takeoff and landing operations [10], [21], and [11]. Additionally, they are often more expensive than multi-rotor unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), and they are unable to hold the capability of protracted hovering over a particular geographical place in the same way that multi-rotor UAVs are able to achieve. For example, a model of an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) with fixed wings may be shown in figure 1[b]. Fixed-wing unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have the ability to glide through the air in a smooth way, which enhances their energy efficiency [20][12]. This is in addition to the fact that they are able to carry bigger payloads. There is also the possibility that fixed-wing unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) might benefit from gliding in order to achieve higher speeds with their vehicles. When it comes to takeoff and landing, it is true that they need a larger area. However, it is also true that they are unable to hover over a certain spot. These unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have the ability to fly great distances and carry a large payload at a maximum speed of 500 kilometres per hour, which is one of the most important benefits of this kind of UAV. With these particular unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), there are a number of restrictions that are linked with them. These restrictions include the fact that they are only capable of doing horizontal takeoffs, which requires a substantial amount of room for taking off, as well as their high cost.

Table1 Different Types of UAV and its Characteristics

S.No	UAV Type	Characteristics of UAV				
		Fly Time [Min]	Speed [Km/h]	Range [Km]	Weight [Kg]	Payload [Kg]
1	Multi - Copter	0 - 60	0 -160	0 -10	0 - 25	0 - 5
2	Fixed Wing	0 - 2000	0 - 500	0 -1850	0.5 - 2500	0- 1500
3	Helicopter	0 - 250	0 - 120	0 - 400	25 - 200	0 - 65

2.3 Hybrid Wing UAV

One kind of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) that is hybrid is a helicopter. The aforementioned two approaches are represented by this specific kind of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), which comes with the flexibility to switch between the two approaches. One example of a hybrid wing unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) is seen in figure 1[c]. An example of this occurrence is the Parrot version, capable of conducting a vertical take-off, manoeuvring along its trajectory, and then transitioning back to hovering by virtue of its rotors[13]. They are able to vertically take off and land because to their tail wings, which also let them to glide through the air. Among the most important advantages are the tremendous vertical payload lift, the easy deployment, and the amazing manoeuvrability [15]. Not only are these specific unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) expensive, but they also need a significant amount of maintenance.

3. UAV Navigation Model

The UAV navigation systems are of various types, each with its own set of navigating parameters: inertia-based, signal-based, and vision-based. The figure 2 clearly shows the different UAV navigation. The Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) primarily employ gyroscopes, accelerometers, and altimeters to direct the onboard flight controller for inertia-based navigation [14][16]. Examples of applications that fall under the category of outdoor navigation includes monitoring, shipment of products, location-based targeting, and public auditing. On the other hand, examples of applications that fall under the category, of inside navigation involve indoor visualisation, automation in factories, and indoor spying. In addition, the navigation processes of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) may be classified according

to the navigation parameters, which include inertia-based, signal-based, and vision-based navigation. When linked to cellular networks, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) that are based on inertia make use of GPS modules and a remote radio head (RRH) for signal-based navigation. Additionally, cameras are used for vision-based navigation [17]. In the beginning, the sensors provide the altitude and horizontal controllers with data.

Figure 2 Categories of UAV Navigation based on Navigation Parameter

These controllers eventually guide the pitch and yaw controllers depending on the route planning that is supposed to be carried out. Following this, the tilt and rotation controllers guide the wings and flaps in manoeuvring the UAV according to the information from sensors.

4. Optimization Approach

The classic mathematical problem-solving methods that are used in (AI) artificial intelligence are referred to as optimization-based approaches. The figure clearly differentiates the various UAV approach based on AI. However, these algorithms have significantly high complexity in terms of both temporal and spatial aspects.

4.1 The Particle Swam Optimization (PSO)

Eberhart and Kennedy introduced (PSO) Particle Swam Optimization in the year 1995. PSO is a population-based search strategy that mimics the hierarchical organisation of a wide variety of animal species, including those of birds and bee species. Every individual animal in PSO may be represented as vector particles within a space of three dimensions Particle Swam Optimization (PSO) calculates the motion of a particle based on its present location and speed [19]. The optimum point of PSO is reached when it attains its objective or minimizes the error to the lowest possibility. The PSO model directs the mobility of UAVs in a three-dimensional environment by treating them as particles. The figure 3 shows the beginning stage (i.e) before particle swam optimization and after particle swam optimization. Autor Jalal modified the conventional Particle Swarm Optimization technique to enable offline navigation of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) while avoiding obstacles such as walls. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is an algorithm that is changed by adding an additional error factor to assure convergence. The modified PSO (MPSO) method functions in a manner that is fundamentally comparable to that of a regular PSO algorithm.

Figure 3 Particle Swam Optimization

First and foremost, the error factor is responsible for converting the routes that are created by Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) that are not feasible into routes that are feasible [18]. MPSO is responsible for relocating and re-initializing particles that are located inside an obstacle boundary in order to achieve maximal efficiency. By doing simulations of circumstances with a single barrier as well as situations with many obstacles, the authors demonstrated that the MPSO method was indeed successful. To solve the problem of UAV route planning, Phung et al. modified the conventional continuous PSO algorithm into discrete PSO (DPSO) [20]. Discrete 3D space and barriers were taken into consideration when the researchers defined the UAV path planning problem as a Travelling Salesman problem (TSP). The use of randomized mutation, boundary shifting, probabilistic initialization, and concurrent deployment of GPU approaches further accelerated the convergence of the DPSO. [21][13]. Huang et al. introduced a competition strategy-based Particle Swarm Optimization (GBPSO) method for choosing the optimal route for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). The suggested competition method evaluates the existing global route in comparison to other potential global paths in order to choose the most efficient path for particles.

4.2: Ant Colony Optimization (ACO)

Coloni et al. made the initial suggestion for ACO in the year 1991 and intended in the direction to address NP hard optimization issues. As its name implies, ACO was inspired by the food hunting strategy of ants. Ants resort to a traditional volatile chemical known as pheromone to communicate and cooperate in their quest for food. Initially, ants start a search for pathways leading to the food source and emit pheromones along their route [24]. Once one ant reaches the food source, other ants monitor the pheromone trails and choose other paths to get the food source. Consequently, the ants will choose for a more straightforward path that contains a higher concentration of pheromone. Furthermore, the levels of pheromones concentration on the deserted routes decrease with time [22], [23]. The figure 5 clearly demonstrates the role ant colony optimization. Cekmez et al. proposed a multi-colony Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) method for autonomous UAV positioning, particularly tailored to evade obstacles in a three-dimensional environment. The authors' study demonstrates that multi-colony ACO optimally resolves the problem of early convergence that occurs with single-colony ACO. The authors first conceptualized the UAV navigation problem as a Travelling Salesman problem (TSP), and thereafter many UAV groups proceeded to seek for the most optimal routes to the intended destination.

Figure 4 UAV Navigation Based on AI Approaches

Figure 5 Ant Colony Optimization

In multi-colony aerial colony operations (ACO), the unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have the responsibility of exchanging pheromone values both inside and across colonies. Guan et al. introduced a double-colony acoustic coupling optimized (ACO) system that uses the genetic algorithm (GA) to produce pheromones. Jin et al. introduced a novel amalgamation of genetic algorithm [25]. The

potential field (APF) and ACO are coupled to form potential field ACO (PFACO) in order to address the issue of early convergence. An Obstacle Perception Function (APF) is an algorithm designed to optimize the speed and safety of an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) in an environment characterized by gravitational and repulsive forces. Moreover, the APF adjusts the likelihood of a UAV transitioning from one node to another in ACO in order to enhance global searching operations [27]. Furthermore, the authors used the Min-Max Ant System (MMAS) to determine the optimal route as well as the least optimal path. In order to get faster convergence, lower the intensity of the least optimal route in accordance with the changes in the global pheromone value.

4.3. The Genetic Algorithm (GA)

In order to do stochastic optimization, the Genetic Algorithm (GA) starts with a population of chromosomes generated at random referred to as the beginning population. Each chromosomal gene consists of a sequence of integer values. Each chromosome or person in this research represents a trajectory of a UAV that is limited by the UAV platform dynamics [26]. The figure 6 shows the flow of genetic algorithm. Every generation will see frequent population modification due to the effects of genomic processes such as the crossover, selection, mutation, insertion, and deletion [12]. Using a fitness function, the modified chromosomes will be selected. Goal is to minimise the fitness function by identifying the chromosome with the nearly lowest fitness value. Therefore, the chromosomes achieve a fairly optimal solution. In order to tackle the NP-hard problem of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) navigation, Bagherian used genetic algorithms (GA). As shown in Figure 6, the author begins by converting the three-dimensional position of the unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) into chromosomes. These chromosomes include the accelerated motions, rate of ascending angle, and rate of heading angle of the UAV at certain time intervals.

Figure 6 Genetic Algorithm for UAV

The chromosome is currently being decoded to obtain three-dimensional coordinates for the UAV in the subsequent time phase. Subsequently, the three dimensional coordinate is assessed by a fitness function that takes into account the and the repercussions of the distance that separates two places, the overall length of the route, the height, and any obstructions. Next, the genetic operations are executed, with selection involving the selection of pathways, crossover involving the exchange of path information, insertion, deletion, managing the maintenance of path information, mutation and addressing the loss of information, [28]. The author Tao et al. enhanced the genetic algorithm by developing a time-limited route that is derived from the vector used for encoding. Each unique guidance path incorporates not only the position information of the guide point but also the status variables. Therefore, it examines if the path between the connecting point and the successive guide points has the lowest possible performance cost, and it monitors the feasibility of the guiding point

by determining whether or not it meets the constraint requirement [29]. The feasibility of the time-limited route depends on the reliability of all the guiding points. This encoding technique relies on the variation in the sequence of UAV yaw angles. The researchers Yang et al. presented a Hierarchical Recursive Multi Agent Genetic Algorithm, which they referred as the HR-MAGA. Within the HR-MAGA development process, agents are able to see the surroundings, establish communication with their neighboring agents. Furthermore, they may minimize their losses by using the correct operators who quickly detect an effective solution. In addition, the hierarchical recursive process is incorporated by HR-MAGA to optimize the local route and obtain a more refined path. Gao et al. introduced the Optimal Chaos Searching Genetic Algorithm (OCGA) as an alternative approach to accelerate convergence. An inverse and chaotic search algorithm is used to generate a superior quality beginning population. Chaos search may include a defined bandwidth of solutions. According to the concept of chaotic searching, contrary searching may generate more suitable reversal sequences. A critical characteristic of optimization is the rate of convergence.

4.4 Grey Wolf Optimization

In 2014, the concept of Grey Wolf Optimization was first presented, taking cues from the way grey wolves seek prey. Grey wolves are socially structured into four distinct classifications: alpha, beta, delta, and omega. The alpha kind set wolves serve as the head, providing guidance and assistance to other set in decision-making [30]. The alpha, beta, and delta kind set initialize a stochastic hunt for the static target, while the omega wolves patiently wait for the instruction to mingle. The figure 7 shows the overall process of grey wolf optimization. Ensuring the identification of the target belonging to the alpha group takes precedence over that of the beta and delta groups. Following the identification of the prey, the head wolves transmit informations to other wolves to mingle with them in the process of target hunting.

Figure 7 Grey Wolf Optimization

The parameters of GWO are limited to two: A, which governs exploitation and exploration B, which aids the wolves in avoiding barriers throughout the search. Zhang et al. used traditional Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) to address the two dimensional route planning challenge of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) with the objective of keeping fuel consumption to a minimum and eliminating any potential threats. An analysis was conducted by the authors to compare GWO with other optimization techniques, namely Ant Colony Optimization, Particle Swam Optimization, and the Cuckoo Search in various situations. In their study, Dewangan et al. used traditional Grey Wolf optimization (GWO) to address the 3D route planning challenge of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) while ensuring obstacle avoidance. In three distinct maps, the authors conducted a comparative analysis of 3D GWO and other optimization techniques. Que et al. introduced a hybrid Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) method called HSGWO-MSOS, which incorporates a modified symbiotic organism’s search (MSOS) for UAV route planning. The authors integrated GWO and MSOS to achieve rapid convergence and effective

exploitation of both global and local environments. Ultimately, they examined the intricacy of HSGWO-MSOS and demonstrated that it surpassed the synthetic aperture (SA) method.

4.5 The Cuckoo Search Algorithm

The algorithm known as Cuckoo Search is designed to simulate the natural process of egg laying that occurs in cuckoo bird. The bird, cuckoo use Levy flying to roam aimlessly in search of a nest, where it deposits its eggs. Both regular short flights and occasional lengthy flights that use the distribution of levies is referred to as levy flights [26]. The figure 8 shows the approach of cuckoo search algorithm. The Cuckoo Search algorithm primarily adheres to three principles: each cuckoo chooses a nest at random and deposits one egg at a time; the nest that contains the egg of the highest quality is passed on to the subsequent generation; and the fixed total number of host nests is determined by the probability of egg uncertainty being either zero or one. [25]. Egg doubt refers to the process of a host bird detecting the eggs of the cuckoo. Under these circumstances, the host has the option to either deposit eggs or permanently depart from the nest. When it comes to the navigation of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), UAVs are like cuckoo drones, and the coordinates are meant to represent nests.

Figure 8 Cuckoo Search Algorithm

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) choose a nest as coordinate using random selection to reach the target site. The target position may either stay constant or dynamically vary based on the mission of the UAV [26]. Should an impediment obstruct the coordinate, the UAV will choose an alternative nest or point in order to reach the intended destination. The coordinate is regarded as the optimal answer and is passed on to the next generation for use in determining the subsequent coordinate. For the purpose of UAV route planning, Xie and Zheng proposed an improved CS algorithm that make use of genetic operators. In order to enhance the convergence of the algorithm and prevent the occurrence of local optima, the authors integrated crossover and mutation operators of the genetic algorithm (GA) with the Cuckoo Search (CS) algorithm[27]. Conversely, Hu et al. used a traditional CS algorithm to plan the trajectory of UAVs in an urban environment. Each egg in the algorithm represents a trajectory and each trajectory contains many coordinates. According to the author, Chevyshev collocation points were utilized as a representation of the coordinates in order to reduce the amount of computing that was required. Further, they demonstrated that by using ideal settings, the CS may surpass the PSO algorithm in performance.

4.6 Pigeon-Inspired Optimization (PIO)

The most common bird species on Earth is pigeons, were originally used by ancient Egyptians for the purpose of conveying messages and carrying out various military missions. Pigeons rely on three homing aids, namely the magnetic field, the sun, and landmarks, to efficiently navigate

towards their home. The core pigeon-inspired optimisation algorithm is primarily governed by two operators: the map and compass operator and the landmark operator. This algorithm is derived from the phenomenon of pigeon self-navigation and the pigeon's ability to navigate itself. Pigeons in their natural habitat go through many phases of nerve feedback during the process of homing, use magnetic fields and landmarks to determine their flight trajectory. The map and compass operators depict the magnetic field component that arises in the early phases. The map and compass operator facilitates the virtual pigeons in independently determining their position and computing their velocity[15]. While the conventional PIO has shown its superiority in many aspects, it also has notable shortcomings, including a lack of variety and immaturity. A Social-Class PIO (SCPIO) was created by Zhang et al. to work around the problems with regular PIO when it comes to autonomous multi-UAV navigation. The pigeons were arranged by the authors into multiple social class strata, with the lowest-class pigeons following the highest-class pigeon. The transition of pigeons across classes is contingent upon the acquisition of the most efficient route. To solve the problems of PIO for unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) navigation and control, Hu et al. introduced an Adaptive Operator Quantum-Behaved PIO (AOQPIO) that incorporates adaptive operators. Furthermore, the authors used chaotic techniques to pre-generate initial solutions in order to get a broader coverage of the solution space. Chaotic behavior refers to the seemingly unpredictable movement seen in a crucial dynamic system. Chaotic motion is characterized by the main effects such as a high sensitivity to initial values, periodicity of motion paths, and (23) the process of randomisation.

4.7 The Dijkstra's and A* Algorithm

Dijkstra, a well-known Danish mathematical researcher and computer scientist, is the one who came up with this method. A wide range of applications, including navigation, use algorithms. The algorithm developed by Dijkstra begins by selecting a starting point that is preferred. It is considered that all the other nodes are indefinitely distant. As the nodes are approached, the distances are continuously updated to reflect the new information. The method developed by Dijkstra analyses the neighbours that exit a node at each iteration. If a shorter route is found, the distances between these neighbours are adjusted [19]. The A* algorithm is a fusion of Dijkstra's algorithm and the approach of greedy best-first-search by including a heuristic to guide itself in addition to finding the shortest route [21]. In order to help autonomous UAV navigation avoid obstacles, the A* method combines the data used by Dijkstra's algorithm, which prioritises nodes close to the origin, with the data used by greedy best first-search, which prioritises nodes close to the destination. Several authors have proposed different versions of these algorithms that incorporate target tracking and real-time environmental updates. Nevertheless, these two methods exhibit a high level of complexity in comparison to other optimization-based methodologies.

5. Learning-Based Approaches

Learning-based approaches refer to the traditional artificial intelligence applications that are based on models. For every given NP-hard issue, these algorithms may provide near optimum solutions with extremely little complexity. A concise overview of the learning-based artificial intelligence methods that are commonly used for the navigation of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) is provided in the following section. These methods include the Markov Decision Process, the Partially Observable Markov Decision Process, Deep Reinforcement Learning, Deep Learning, and Asynchronous Advantage Actor-Critic.

5.1 Deep Reinforcement Learning

The DRL employs Q-values similarly to Q-learning, with the omission of the Q-table component. To guarantee the scalability of Reinforcement Learning (RL), the Q-table is substituted by a Deep Neural Network (DNN). An essential goal of a Deep Neural Network (DNN) is to acquire knowledge from the data in order to eliminate the need for repetitive human computations. A Deep Neural Network (DNN) is a non-linear computing model capable of training and performing tasks analogous to the structure of the human brain, which includes decision-making, prediction, identification, and visualisation are all included in this category [23]. In contrast to RL, DRL employs distinct decision-making processes.

5.1.1 The Markov Decision Process

The Markov Decision Process is a decision-making technique often used in reinforcement learning. Yet, DRL may also use the Markov Decision Process environment for navigation of unmanned aerial vehicle. Here, training the agent is accomplished by the use of two deep neural networks. There is one that serves as the policy DNN, while the other serves as the objective DNN. The MDP-based duelling deep DQN technique for concurrent UAV direction-finding and radio mapping in a three dimensional space was separated the activity into discrete components and used the artificial neural network to estimate the flying direction. By contrast, Huang et al. used massive MIMO communication to direct UAVs along their best route using MDP-based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL). Abedin et al. introduced a Model Decompositional Optimisation (MDP)-based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) method for UAV-BS navigation, taking into account the freshness of data and energy efficiency. By using Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) with experience replay memory, the authors formulated the UAV-BS navigation issue as an NP-hard problem. An MDP-based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) method for the urban vehicular network was suggested by Oubbati et al. The objective of this approach is to use numerous UAVs to minimise the average energy consumption and maximize the vehicle coverage. They contemplated using centralised training for the UAVs to efficiently cover a large number of vehicles with the fewest UAVs, while ensuring precision in avoiding barriers and accidents. Oubbati et al. introduced a Multi-Agent DQN (MADQN) architecture based on Markov Decision Process (MDP). This method employs two Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) to traverse several Internet of Things (IoT) devices. The objective is to minimise the age of information (AoI) and enhance wireless powered communication networks. (WPCN). In order to optimise energy economy and prevent a collision, they used a centralised training approach for the UAVs. In addition, Wang et al. introduced an autonomous UAV navigation system that avoids obstacles by using MDP-based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) with very low incentives using non-expert helpers (LwH). Learning with Heading establishes procedures before Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) training, allowing the agent to attain optimality through the formulation of dynamic learning objectives. An author introduced a CNN-based double DQN (DDQN) protocol for planning UAV coverage paths, taking into account energy consumption and map-based mobility. Conversely, He et al. introduced a vision-based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) technique to address the navigation issue. A twin delayed deep deterministic policy gradient (TD3) is used from a demonstration, a convolutional neural network (CNN) is used, and a Markov decision process (MDP) is used to simulate the navigation problem. [15]. Object detection-assisted Markov Decision Process (MDP)-based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) for collision-free autonomous UAV navigation was suggested by Chen et al. in reference [13]. To attain expedited convergence, the authors considered the spatial positions of the objects, the orientation angle and velocity of the UAV, and the two-dimensional coordinates within the state space.

5.1.2: The Partially Observable Markov Decision Process

A modification of the Markov Decision Process (MDP) known as POMDP allows the agent to monitor the environment without knowledge of its true state and then implement actions. POMDP takes into account all the uncertainties of the environment that may affect the estimation of actions. The observation, the status, and the action are the three primary component space of POMDP. Despite being a time-intensive process, it may yield greater accuracy in optimality compared to MDP. Walker and colleagues introduced a POMDP-based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) framework for autonomous interior navigation of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) here. The agent employs Markov Decision Process (MDP) for universal route planning and Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP) for local path planning, while systematically circumventing barriers. Additionally, the authors employed trust region policy optimization (TRPO) to govern the policy enhancement process during the learning phases. Pearson et al. employed POMDP to develop a vision-based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) method for autonomous navigation of UAVs. The authors introduced an Extended Double Deep Q-Learning (EDDQN) methodology. This technique employs a modified Q-function that utilizes the surrounding imagery to direct the UAV in region exploration. Theile et al. proposed an autonomous UAV navigation system utilizing POMDP-based DDQN. The primary aim of the UAV is to traverse and gather data from a designated area utilizing the cartographic depiction of the location.

5.2 Asynchronous Advantage Actor-Critic Model

A3C is a stylish Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) technique in which each driving force is composed of two networks: an artist network and a detractor network. The A3C protocol is often used in multi-agent systems. The primary function of the artist network is to monitor the present condition of the environment and choose appropriate actions. Upon completion of the activities, the agents get prizes. The critic network compiles the rewards, actions, states, and subsequent states of all UAVs to provide Q-values and use a deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG) to refine the artist network. In multi-UAV settings, A3C demonstrates exceptional efficiency. Wang and colleagues introduced an A3C-based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) framework for autonomous Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) navigation to facilitate mobile edge computing. Every UAV model comprises a network of critics and actors. All artist networks inside the UAVs are trained with uniform data disseminated throughout the entire network. Detractor networks are trained on individual UAV data via a multi-agent Deep Dynamic Prediction Graph (DDPG). In addition, Wang et al. introduced a Rapid Recurrent Deterministic Policy Gradient algorithm (quick RDPG) for the purpose of guiding UAVs in a vast and intricate environment, while precisely avoiding obstacles. Fast-RDPG is an A3C-based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) online technique designed to efficiently address POMDP issues and achieve quicker convergence. In contrast, Liu et al. introduced an A3C-based Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) technique for decentralised and energy-efficient autonomous Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) navigation. By considering the observations included in the artist network, the authors updated the target network using a modified policy gradient.

5.3. The Deep Learning

Deep learning is the predominant technology employed for vision-based UAV navigation. Deep learning pertains specifically to the deep neural network (DNN) element of the Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) framework. The recent advancements in several tasks including object identification and localisation, an analysis of monocular or stereo pictures for the purpose of image segmentation and depth recognition, researchers have effectively employed the Deep Neural Network (DNN) approach to identify roads and streets on important routes and metropolitan areas [19]. The main

objective is to provide a high degree of autonomy for autonomous vehicles. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) may be used to accomplish autonomous navigation for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) under very challenging conditions. There are many categories of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), including fully connected NN (FNN) and CNN. A CNN-based image augmentation technique for vision-based UAV navigation was presented by Menfoukh. In their study, Back et al. introduced a vision-based UAV navigation system that used Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are able to perform trail following, disturbance recovery, and obstacle avoidance thanks to this system. Within the realm of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), Pearson et al. presented the idea of autonomous trail following and steering through the use of real-time photos and CNN modelling. In order to achieve indoor navigation, Chhikara et al. introduced A Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN-GA) architecture that utilises genetic algorithms (GA) to optimise the hyper-parameters of the networks. Autonomous UAV navigation with transfer learning was accomplished with the help of the DCNN-GA model.

Conclusion

A concise overview of the UAV navigation system and application-based categorization was provided to facilitate researchers' understanding of the ideas presented in this study. A comprehensive overview of optimization-based and learning-based approaches was provided including the underlying concepts, operational principles, and key characteristics of many artificial intelligence algorithms used by various researchers for autonomous UAV navigation. Moreover it also emphasizes current research areas to accelerate the ongoing research on AI-driven autonomous UAV navigation. Unmanned aerial vehicle navigation AI may incur high computational costs, but it enhances the overall performance of UAVs in complex dynamic environments by reducing energy consumption, flight time, and communication delay. Future studies will concentrate on boosting computational efficiency, developing AI models for real-time learning, and ensuring safety and ethical issues when deploying UAVs.

References

1. Y. Lu, X. Zhucun, G.-S. Xia, and L. Zhang, "A survey on vision-based UAV navigation," *Geo-spatial Inf. Sci.*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 1–12, Jan. 2018.
2. P. Grippa, D. Behrens, C. Bettstetter, and F. Wall, "Job selection in a network of autonomous UAVs for delivery of goods," in *Proc. Robot., Sci. Syst. XIII*, Jul. 2017, pp. 1–10, doi: 10.15607/RSS.2017.XIII.018.
3. Z. Huang, C. Chen, and M. Pan, "Multiobjective UAV path planning for emergency information collection and transmission," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 7, no. 8, pp. 6993–7009, Aug. 2020.
4. M. Y. Arafat and S. Moh, "A survey on cluster-based routing protocols for unmanned aerial vehicle networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 498–516, 2018.
5. M. Liu, J. Yang, and G. Gui, "DSF-NOMA: UAV-assisted emergency communication technology in a heterogeneous Internet of Things," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 5508–5519, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2019.2903165.
6. M. Y. Arafat and S. Moh, "Bio-inspired approaches for energy-efficient localization and clustering in UAV networks for monitoring wildfires in remote areas," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 18649–18669, 2021.
7. O. M. Bushnaq, A. Chaaban, and T. Y. Al-Naffouri, "The role of UAV IoT networks in future wildfire detection," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 8, no. 23, pp. 16984–16999, Dec. 2021.
8. R. S. de Moraes and E. P. de Freitas, "Multi-UAV based crowd monitoring system," *IEEE Trans. Aerosp. Electron. Syst.*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 1332–1345, Apr. 2020.

9. M. Wan, G. Gu, W. Qian, K. Ren, X. Maldague, and Q. Chen, "Unmanned aerial vehicle video-based target tracking algorithm using sparse representation," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 9689–9706, Dec. 2019.
10. S. H. Chung, B. Sah, and J. Lee, "Optimization for drone and drone-truck combined operations: A review of the state of the art and future directions," *Comput. Oper. Res.*, vol. 123, Nov. 2020, Art. no. 105004.
11. C. Wu, B. Ju, Y. Wu, X. Lin, N. Xiong, and G. X. Xu Liang, "UAV autonomous target search based on deep reinforcement learning in complex disaster scene," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 117227–117245, 2019.
12. B. Wang, Y. Sun, Z. Sun, L. D. Nguyen, and T. Q. Duong, "UAV assisted emergency communications in social IoT: A dynamic hypergraph coloring approach," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 7, no. 8, pp. 7663–7677, Aug. 2020.
13. O. Esrafilian, R. Gangula, and D. Gesbert, "Three-dimensional-map based trajectory design in UAV-aided wireless localization systems," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 9894–9904, Jun. 2021.
14. R. Chen, B. Yang, and W. Zhang, "Distributed and collaborative localization for swarming UAVs," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 5062–5074, Mar. 2021.
15. N. Gageik, P. Benz, and S. Montenegro, "Obstacle detection and collision avoidance for a UAV with complementary low-cost sensors," *IEEE Access*, vol. 3, pp. 599–609, 2015.
16. Y. Zeng, R. Zhang, and T. J. Lim, "Wireless communications with unmanned aerial vehicles: Opportunities and challenges," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 54, no. 5, pp. 36–42, May 2016.
17. B. Li, Z. Fei, and Y. Zhang, "UAV communications for 5G and beyond: Recent advances and future trends," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 2241–2263, Apr. 2019.
18. S. Rezwan and W. Choi, "Priority-based joint resource allocation with deep Q-Learning for heterogeneous NOMA systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 41468–41481, 2021.
19. S. Yan, M. Peng, and X. Cao, "A game theory approach for joint access selection and resource allocation in UAV assisted IoT communication networks," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 1663–1674, Apr. 2019.
20. M. Mozaffari, W. Saad, M. Bennis, and M. Debbah, "Wireless communication using unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): Optimal transport theory for hover time optimization," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 16, no. 12, pp. 8052–8066, Dec. 2017.
21. C. Wang, J. Wang, J. Wang, and X. Zhang, "Deep-reinforcement-learning based autonomous UAV navigation with sparse rewards," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 7, no. 7, pp. 6180–6190, Jul. 2020.
22. M. E. Morocho-Cayamcela, H. Lee, and W. Lim, "Machine learning for 5G/B5G mobile and wireless communications: Potential, limitations, and future directions," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 137184–137206, 2019.
23. M. Sheraz, M. Ahmed, X. Hou, Y. Li, D. Jin, Z. Han, and T. Jiang, "Artificial intelligence for wireless caching: Schemes, performance, and challenges," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 631–661, 1st Quart., 2021.
24. G. Villarrubia, J. F. De Paz, P. Chamoso, and F. D. la Prieta, "Artificial neural networks used in optimization problems," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 272, pp. 10–16, Jan. 2018.
25. B. Liu, L. Wang, and M. Liu, "Lifelong federated reinforcement learning: A learning architecture for navigation in cloud robotic systems," *IEEE Robot. Autom. Lett.*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 4555–4562, Oct. 2019.
26. O. Souissi, R. Benatillah, D. Duvivier, A. Artiba, N. Belanger, and P. Feyzeau, "Path planning: A 2013 survey," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Ind. Eng. Syst. Manage.*, 2013, pp. 1–8.

27. P. B. Sujit, S. Saripalli, and J. B. Sousa, "Unmanned aerial vehicle path following: A survey and analysis of algorithms for fixed-wing unmanned aerial vehicles," *IEEE Control Syst.*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 42–59, Feb. 2014.
28. P. Pandey, A. Shukla, and R. Tiwari, "Aerial path planning using meta heuristics: A survey," in *Proc. 2nd Int. Conf. Electr., Comput. Commun. Technol. (ICECCT)*, Feb. 2017, pp. 1–7.
29. M. Ponsen, M. E. Taylor, and K. Tuyls, "Abstraction and generalization in reinforcement learning: A summary and framework," in *Adaptive and Learning Agents*, M. E. Taylor and K. Tuyls, Eds. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2010, pp. 1–32.
30. S. Rezwani and W. Choi, "A survey on applications of reinforcement learning in flying ad-hoc networks," *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 4, p. 449, Feb. 2021, doi:10.3390/e10040449.